

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Staneart****FIRST NAME: Steve****PROGRAM CODE: MCCT****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did not use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 8

QUIZ: INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC AND PROFESSIONAL PAPER WRITING

1. **Turabian style was adapted from which citation style used frequently by authors of book manuscripts?**
 - A. APA style
 - B. MLA style
 - C. Chicago Style¹
 - D. Oxford Style

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press. 2013), 13.

2. **According to Turabian, “good writing”**
- A. Lists a series of facts, demonstrating the breadth of knowledge the writer has achieved
 - B. Enters into a conversation with the reader²**
 - C. Uses long, complex sentences
 - D. Employs the use of a multitude of styles in a single paper
3. **The Turabian style, in-text (Parenthetical) Citations are often used by students of which disciplines?**
- A. The natural, physical, and social sciences³**
 - B. All PhD level writing, including dissertations
 - C. Mathematics and Linguistics
 - D. Law and International Treaties
4. **The European Union Writing Style is most like:**
- A. The Harvard Style
 - B. The Oxford Style⁴**
 - C. The American Psychological Association (APA) Style
 - D. The African Union Style
5. **Which of the following is the correct way to use quotation marks and a period (all stop) in a sentence, using American writing style?**
- A. ‘The boy kicked the ball’.
 - B. “The boy kicked the ball”.
 - C. ‘The boy kicked the ball.’

- D. “The boy kicked the ball.”⁵**
6. **In the mandated WORD template, on a response paper, all in-text script should be which font and size?**
- Calibri, 14
- Times New Roman, 12⁶**
- Turabian, 12
- Collegiate, 11
7. **Plagiarism is avoided by accurately documenting sources. Which is the correct way to cite a book by four or more authors in a bibliography according to Turabian style?**
- Edward O. Laumann et al., The Social Organization of Sexuality: Sexual Practices in the United States (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1994), 262
- Edward O. Laumann et al., *The Social Organization of Sexuality: Sexual Practices in the United States* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1994), 262⁷**
- Laumann, Edward O., John H. Gagnon, Robert T. Michael, and Stuart Michaels, (1994) *The Social Organization of Sexuality: Sexual Practices in the United States*, Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

⁵ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1. 3rd ed.* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 35.

⁶ Turabian, 395

⁷ Library Guides Bennett Edu, “Chicago/Turabian Style.” *Holgate Library Research Guides*. <http://libraryguides.bennett.edu/home/writing/chicago-turabian-style/turabian-style-footnotesendnotes--bibliography> (accessed April 24, 2021)

Edward O. Laumann et al., **The Social Organization of Sexuality: Sexual Practices in the United States** (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1994), 262

8. **Which of the following is a computer application used by Euclid University for managing citations in international academic and professional papers?**

Purdue Online Writing Lab

Zotero⁸

Open Office

ProofreadBot

9. **In the “styles ribbon” in WORD, options are presented by which the student/author should organize the response paper. Which option should be used to indicate a new major thought?**

A. RP Heading 1⁹

B. RP Heading 2

C. RP Heading 3

D. RP Normal

⁸ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *How to Write a Response Paper*. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021, 10.

⁹ Cleenewerck and Gulma. *How to Write a Response Paper*, 4.

10. **The use of a first-person pronoun, while controversial in formal academic work, is encouraged in response papers. It helps the instructor understand how the student is interacting with the material. Which of the following is a good example of using a first-person pronoun?**

- A. "I believe the following..."
- B. "I think this is best..."
- C. **"I have demonstrated..."**¹⁰
- D. "When I examined the material..."

¹⁰ Turabian, 248.

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